

Measurement of Service Quality Perception, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty in PT Medika Antapani

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ABSTRACT: Indonesia had 11,347 clinics in 2020, 10,238 Pratama, and 1,109 Utama. West Java Province had the most clinics in 2021, with 6,572 Pratama and 1,042 Utama. Private Bandung public health provider PT. Medika Antapani 2020–2021 customer visits decreased. Pratama clinics in Kiaracandong have almost doubled to 15 clinics, giving cash clients many options. To compete, health services must constantly improve service quality to satisfy customers and build loyalty.

This research helps PT. Medika Antapani meet customer service needs. The author uses a descriptive and causal research design. The author distributes Likert scale questionnaires to 200 respondents who meet the criteria. According to a descriptive analysis of 200 respondents, most are male, 60-74 years old, live in Cisaranten Endah, are employees, and use general practitioner services. The total average for causal analysis was 3,088, 3,127, and 2.93 for service quality, satisfaction, and loyalty. Satisfaction and service quality affect loyalty by 84.1%.

Service quality improvements are needed in PT Medika Antapani for addressing six areas, including low scores on the latest equipment, recruiting Ob-Gyn doctors, and providing reminder messages. For future recommendations, PT Medika Antapani must evaluate its services to maintain quality and develop in areas service users need.

KEYWORDS: Loyalty, Service Quality, Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

In 2020, the Indonesian Ministry of Health reported 11,347 government and community-owned clinics, including 10,238 Pratama Clinic and 1,109 Utama Clinic. North Sumatra Province, with 1,565 clinics (1,491 Pratama Clinic and 74 Utama Clinic), has the most. Pratama clinics provide basic medical services, while Utama clinics provide specialist medical services or both. According to Indonesia Ministry of Health (Setiaji, 2022), 6,572 Pratama and 1,042 Utama clinics provided clinical services in 2021. The most clinics are in West Java Province, with 1,623 Pratama and 190 Utama clinics. West Java has seen a significant increase in clinics despite a nationwide decrease.

PT. Medika Antapani as Arima Pharmacy founded in 1989 on Kiaracandong, Bandung (with medicine center). PT Medika Antapani was established as a legal company in October 2005 to grow to meet public health service needs. To date, PT. Medika Antapani has been a clinic in Bandung that provides comprehensive services, basic and necessary general services (general doctors, general dentists), home care services, Imunicare (Immunization), and independent midwife practice in Pratama Clinic Medika Antapani (KPMA), and group practices of specialist doctors in Utama Clinic Medika Antapani (Company Profile PT. Medika Antapani, 2022).

PT. Medika Antapani saw fewer patient visits before and during the COVID-19 pandemic (2018–2020) many people avoided health services during the pandemic because they had to follow strict health protocols and perform Covid-19 checks.

Figure 1. Visit Chart PT. Medika Antapani

Source: Recap data PT Medika Antapani’s yearly client visits, 2022

In 2022, KUMA-1 general practitioner services moved to KPMA, bringing cash, BPJS, and insurance clients together. However, at KUMA-1, cash clients had their own polyclinic, so queues were short. This service transfer reduces cash client visits, hurting PT Medika Antapani's direct profit. PT. Medika Antapani also received complaints. Additionally, unit pharmacy-2, which only accepts prescriptions from cash clients who directly profit to PT Medika Antapani has decreased.

PT. Medika Antapani lost profit revenue due to client cash shortages. Cash clients also have more clinic options in Kiaracandong. In 2021, BPS data showed 8 clinics in the Kiaracandong sub-district, but by 2022, there were 15. Medika Antapani Pratama Clinic unit is competitive. Pratama Medika Antapani Clinic competes with the 1.7km away Pratama Famili Sehat Clinic in Kiaracandong. PT. Medika Antapani also competes with the Khalisa Medika Pratama Clinic, 500m from Kiaracandong, in the Antapani District. The Antapani Medika Utama Clinic unit competes with hospitals with more specialists. Cash clients who leave PT. Medika Antapani after a bad experience may also reduce visits.

To keep customers coming back and recommending PT. Medika Antapani, service quality must be improved. Service quality affects customer satisfaction, which affects customer loyalty, according to numerous studies. The authors want to know how PT Medika Antapani's service quality and cash client satisfaction affect customer loyalty.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Actions, activities, and performances performed by one entity or person for and/or with another entity or person are referred to as services (Zeithaml et al., 2017). An extensive definition contains "All economic actions result in a non-physical product or structure that is generally consumed at the moment of production and provides added value in forms (such as convenience, amusement, timeliness, comfort, or health) that are fundamentally intangible to the first consumer."

According to the definitions of service quality, this is the outcome of a comparison between a customer's expectations (A Parasuraman et al., 1986) for a service and their impression of how the service was executed. A business with superior service quality regularly meets or exceeds client expectations. In instances where customer satisfaction and service quality diverge, clients develop their performance expectations for their future purchases based on service quality as the more solid perception.

Customer satisfaction is the result of several customer-product interactions in which customers evaluate the service performance they have got and compare it to their expectations. The expectancy/disconfirmation paradigm in process theory includes four constructs: (1) expectations, (2) performance, (3) disconfirmation, and (4) satisfaction (Mohr, 1992). Customers who are satisfied with their purchases are more likely to return, remain loyal, and suggest a firm to others. Nevertheless, if the service falls short of their expectations, customers may suffer in silence, complain about the service, and transfer providers in the future.

A customer's inclination to continue patronizing a company over the long term, preferably exclusively, and to suggest the company's products to friends and colleagues is loyalty (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2021). Customer loyalty involves preferences, likes, and future intentions in addition to conduct. Moreover, there is a significant correlation between customer happiness and customer

loyalty. This bond is especially robust when clients are really happy. Thus, organizations that only try to please customers may not be doing enough to foster client loyalty; rather, they must aim to go above and beyond or even thrill customers.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research helps PT. Medika Antapani meet customer service needs. The author adopts a conclusive research design to address the research questions in this study. The author collects primary data by distributing research questionnaires. This questionnaire is administered using a Likert scale to 200 respondents who meet the criteria (1) Having obtained services from PT. Medika Antapani, and (2) A client who pays from their own pocket. For secondary data, The author gathered from patient records or papers at the Inpatient Installation of PT Medika Antapani, as well as from books, journals, earlier research, and publicly accessible data used.

This study employs a descriptive and causal research technique because it examines variables and aims to provide a systematic, factual explanation of the facts and the relationship between the analyzed variables. Processing and analysis of the data used is descriptive analysis to determine the description of the sample and the description of each variable. Causal research in this study uses path analysis to find the relationship between service quality, satisfaction, and loyalty cash client variables (Malhotra, 2020).

Figure 2. Path Analysis
Source: Author, 2023

RESULTS

Characteristic of the 200 respondent most are male, 60-74 years old, live in Cisaranten Endah, are employees, and use PT Medika Anatapani’s general practitioner services.

Descriptive analysis

This descriptive analysis is used to determine the distribution and variation of answers from respondents. The distribution of respondents' answers to the perception of service quality, with an average total value on the service quality variable is 3.088 which has sufficient meaning. The three lowest scores are found in the statement that PT. Medika Antapani has the latest equipment, PT. Medika Antapani gives special attention to their clients, and PT. Medika Antapani always reminds their clients for the client must do the next examination. Whereas the highest score on the service quality variable is found in the statement if the clients feel safe to transact at PT. Medika Antapani.

The distribution of respondents' satisfaction ratings, where satisfaction is achieved when reality exceeds expectations. The total score achieved is 3,127 and has meaning just enough; nonetheless, it cannot be argued that cash clients do not yet receive considerable satisfaction

The distribution of respondents' loyalty ratings with an average total value on the service quality variable is 2,93 with has sufficient meaning. In this variable, the three lowest values are as follows: respondents would not move to another place to get

health services; respondents will immediately choose PT. Medika Antapani for treatment; and respondents feel PT. Medika Antapani is the best choice. The responder talks about positive things about PT. Medika Antapani receiving the highest score.

Causal Analysis

Based on the results of data processing, the path coefficient obtained from the Service Quality variable (X) to the Satisfaction variable (Y) is shown in the table below:

Table 1. Coefficients Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.305	.276		1.103	.271
	Service Quality	.294	.009	.924	34.120	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

Source: Data Analysis, 2023

The value of Sig < Alpha (0.000 < 0.05) indicates that the service quality variable strongly influences the satisfaction variable. The standardized coefficient beta value is 0.924, which means that the service quality variable can affect changes in the satisfaction variable by 92.4% indicating a good association between the service quality and satisfaction variables. The remaining 7.6% represents the effect of variables beyond the scope of the study.

Based on the results of data processing, the path coefficient obtained from the Service Quality variable (X) and Satisfaction variable (Y) to Loyalty (Z) is shown in the table below:

Table 2. Coefficients Service Quality and Satisfaction on Loyalty

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.011	.695		-1.455	.147
	Service Quality	.408	.057	.537	7.214	.000
	Satisfaction	.951	.178	.397	5.338	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Loyalty

Source: Data Analysis, 2023

The value of Sig < Alpha (0.000 < 0.05) indicates that the Service Quality and Satisfaction variables strongly influence on the Loyalty variable. The Standardized Coefficient Beta value of the Service Quality variable on Loyalty is 0.537 which means that the service quality variable can affect changes in the loyalty variable by 53.7%, to put it another way, there is a moderate association between the service quality variable and loyalty.

The Satisfaction to Loyalty variable's Standardized Coefficient Beta value is 0.397, indicating that the satisfaction variable has a weak association with loyalty and may affect changes in the loyalty variable by 39.7%. Other variables besides service quality and patient satisfaction variables that might effect patient loyalty account for the remaining amount.

Figure 3. Partial Results of Path Analysis

Source: Data Analysis, 2023

Figure 3. Relationship of Service Quality and Satisfaction to Loyalty

Simultaneous testing is carried out to prove whether together service quality (X) and satisfaction (Y) have a significant effect on loyalty (Z). The test results for these variables are as follows:

Table 3. Simultaneous test of service quality and satisfaction to loyalty

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7340.636	2	3670.318	521.953	.000 ^b
	Residual	1385.284	197	7.032		
	Total	8725.920	199			

a. Dependent Variable: Loyalty

b. Predictors: (Constant), Satisfaction, Service Quality

Source: Data Analysis, 2023

Using the significant value as a guide (Sig.), the Sig value is known to be 0.000 and less than 0.05, the simultaneous test can imply that the service quality variable (X) and satisfaction variable (Y) impact the loyalty variable (Z) concurrently. In addition, based on table IV.9 the computed F value is 521.953, which is more than the F table (2, 198), which is 3.04, suggesting that the variables of service quality (X) and satisfaction (Y) impact the loyalty (Z) concurrently.

Table 4. Summary of service quality and satisfaction to loyalty

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.917 ^a	.841	.840	2.65177

a. Predictors: (Constant), Kepuasan, Kualitas Pelayanan

Source: Data Analysis, 2023

Simultaneously, service quality (X) and satisfaction (Y) affect loyalty (Z) by 0.841, or 84.1%. The remaining 15.9% is influenced by other factors outside this model.

And in conclusion, the final computation of substructure 1 and substructure 2 resulted in the following model:

Figure 4. Path way effect of service quality and satisfaction to loyalty
Source: Data Analysis, 2023

CONCLUSION

The results of descriptive analysis obtained from 200 respondents, that the most respondents are male, with an age category of 60-74, live in Cisaranten Endah, have an employee profession, and use general practitioner services at PT Medika Antapani.

For causal analysis, the following results were obtained:

1. The total average of the service quality variable is 3,088
2. The total average of the satisfaction variable is 3,127,
3. The total average of the loyalty variable is 2.93, and
4. This loyalty variable is greatly influenced simultaneously by the satisfaction and service quality variables which reach 84.1%

These findings support the business issues that exist in PT. Medika Antapani, which has experienced a decrease in visits since 2018 which is marked by a lack of loyalty. So to increase the value of loyalty, it must be started with improvements in service quality variables. The implementation plan for PT. Medika Antapani outlines six elements and improvements that can be made immediately such as low scores regarding the latest equipment, recruiting Ob-Gyn doctors, and providing reminder message service.

The difficult improvement is to improve the dimensions of Pratama Clinic which has a large number of competitors, and moreover, there has just been a unification of all clients to Pratama Clinic which makes clients complain about queuing. Besides that, this improvement requires a lot of time, money and many departments are involved.

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Cite this Article: Yustia Annisaa Thaharoh, Ira Fachira (2023). Measurement of Service Quality Perception, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty in PT Medika Antapani. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(3), 1922-1927